

Sartang Lexicon – Overview file

These files contain the data of the Sartang lexicon. There are data of all four Sartang varieties – Khoina, Khoitam, Jerigaon and Rahung. The metadata of the files can be found in this table:

<i>file name</i>	<i>size (MB)</i>	<i>length (hh:mm:ss)</i>	<i>speaker(s)</i>	<i>location</i>	<i>year of birth/gender</i>	<i>topic</i>
Khoina DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1210113						
SART210514A.wav	233	00:23:09	Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/f	Wordlist 1 human being till 553 brain
SART210514B.wav	467	00:46:14	Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/f	Wordlist 554 forehead till 557 sparrow
SART210514C.wav	429	00:42:32	Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/f	Wordlist 558 bird of prey till 257 thread
SART210514D.wav	214	00:21:14	Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/f	Wordlist 258 sew till 307 different
SART210514E.wav	591	00:58:34	Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/f	Wordlist 308 other till 441 neg imp
SART210514A-E.pdf						lexical list
SART210514A-E.zip	355					cut sound files
SART210514A-E OTHER.zip	11					cut sound files (not on list)
SART220514A.wav	549	00:54:28	Geshi Tamu Yamchodu	Khoina	1958/m	Extra wordlist word till intestines
SART220514B.wav	495	00:49:05	Geshi Tamu Yamchodu, Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/1958/m/f	Extra wordlist vein till suddenly
SART220514C.wav	765	01:15:51	Geshi Tamu Yamchodu, Tshering Dolma Nethungji	Khoina	1958/1958/m/f	Extra wordlist suddenly till turmeric
SART220514.pdf						extra wordlist
SART220514 OTHER.zip	269					cut sound files extra wordlist
Jerigaon DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1210111						
SART110513B2.wav	572	00:56:40	Dorji Khandu	Jerigaon	1964/m	questions on word list
SART110513B2.pdf						lexical list
SART110513B2.zip	15.7					cut sound files
SART230514A.wav	230	00:45:45	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 1 human being till 105 burn
SART230514B.wav	3.98	00:00:47	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 106 extinguished till 108 cloud
SART230514C.wav	16.2	00:03:13	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 110 wind till 158 bear

SART230514D.wav	121	00:24:06	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 159 cow till 218 uncooked rice
SART230514E.wav	20.7	00:04:06	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 221 chili till 231 ripe
SART230514F.wav	25.2	00:50:05	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list animal species, 232 rotten till 307 different
SART230514G.wav	293	00:58:08	Sena Phinju Nathongji	Jerigaon	1978/m	Word list 308 other till 441 neg imp plus directions
SART230514A-G.pdf						lexical list
SART230514A-G.zip	86.5					cut sound files
SART230514H.wav	137	00:27:19	Veena Rockpudu	Jerigaon	1985/f	Word list 1 human being till 111 rain
SART230514I.wav	190	00:37:39	Veena Rockpudu	Jerigaon	1985/f	Wordt list 112 rainbow till 261 weave
SART230514J.wav	188	00:37:25	Veena Rockpudu	Jerigaon	1985/f	Word list 263 rope till 441 neg imp
SART230514H-J.pdf						lexical list
SART230514H-J.zip	70.1					cut sound files
Khoitam DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1210120						
SART240514A.wav	204	00:40:35	Nima Lhamu Chanadok	Khoitam	1989/f	Word list 1 human being till 105 burn
SART240514B.wav	3.40	00:00:40	Nima Lhamu Chanadok	Khoitam	1989/f	Word list 106 extinguished
SART240514C.wav	289	00:57:25	Nima Lhamu Chanadok	Khoitam	1989/f	Word list 107 water till 279 broom
SART240514D.wav	244	00:48:26	Nima Lhamu Chanadok	Khoitam	1989/f	Word list 499 veranda till 441 neg imp
SART240514A-D.pdf						lexical list
SART240514A-D.zip	140					cut sound files
SART250514A.wav	236	00:46:55	Kezang Rokpu	Khoitam	1961/m	Word list 1 human being till 106 extinguished
SART250514B.wav	169	00:31:33	Kezang Rokpu	Khoitam	1961/m	Word list 107 water till 524 taken
SART250514C.wav	273	00:54:05	Kezang Rokpu	Khoitam	1961/m	Word list 525 langur till 307 different
SART250514D.wav	276	00:54:43	Kezang Rokpu	Khoitam	1961/m	Word list 308 other till 441 neg imp
SART250514A-D.pdf						lexical list
SART250514A-D.zip	162					cut sound files
SART250514E.wav	783	02:35:19	Kezang Rokpu	Khoitam	1961/m	Extra list Sartang
SART250514E.pdf						extra list

SART250514E.zip	103					cut sound files extra list
Rahung DOI http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1210122						
SART290514A.wav	724	01:11	Karma Tsering Ngoimu	Rahung	1953/m	Word list 1 human being till 186 tree
SART290514B.wav	456	00:45:13	Karma Tsering Ngoimu	Rahung	1953/m	Word list 186 tree till 364 fall
SART290514C.wav	283	00:23:35	Karma Tsering Ngoimu	Rahung	1953/m	Word list 364 swim till 441 neg imp plus exonyms
SART290514A-C.pdf						lexical list
SART290514A-C.zip	216					cut sound files
SART290514D.wav	270	00:26:45	Karma Tsering Ngoimu	Rahung	1953/m	Extra word list word till floor
SART290514E.wav	427	00:42:19	Karma Tsering Ngoimu	Rahung	1953/m	Extra word list hearth tray till turmeric
SART290514D-E.pdf						extra list
SART290514D-E.zip	108					cut sound files extra list
SART290514F.wav	251	00:24:56	Dolma Sarmu	Rahung	1927/f	Word list 1 human being till 553 brain
SART290514G.wav	387	00:38:21	Dolma Sarmu	Rahung	1927/f	Word list 554 forehead till 148 cockroach
SART290514H.wav	575	00:56:58	Tsomu Sarmu	Rahung	1994/f	Word list 149 spider till 319 soft
SART290514I.wav	344	00:34:07	Tsomu Sarmu	Rahung	1994/f	Word list 320 new till 441 neg imp
SART290514F-I.pdf						lexical list
SART290514F-I.zip	436					cut sound files